

Students' representations of academic law writing in Morocco: Obstacles and challenges to the appropriation of legal genres

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Abstract

This article looks at how Moroccan undergraduate law students perceive academic writing, and the difficulties they encounter in appropriating the legal genres specific to their training (dissertation, commentary on judgments, case studies). Based on a survey of 80 students from several Moroccan faculties, the results show that these representations, often inherited from high school, hinder students' understanding of academic expectations and the adoption of appropriate writing strategies. The study also highlights the lack of methodological support felt by students, and the strong demand for structured teaching methods. These findings open up avenues for a pedagogy of academic writing in law better adapted to the Moroccan context, favoring students' academic success.

Keywords: academic writing, law students, representations, legal genres, university pedagogy.

1. Introduction

The Moroccan university system is expanding rapidly, welcoming a growing number of students each year from a variety of social and cultural backgrounds. This diversification brings with it numerous challenges in terms of the quality of teaching and student support, particularly in view of the ever-increasing demands of university courses. In this context, academic success is a major challenge for students, institutions and educational players alike, who must ensure that knowledge is properly consolidated, that training is solid and that students successfully enter the job market.

In legal studies, these issues take on a significant dimension through the need to master academic writing, which is a fundamental lever for communication, analysis and disciplinary reflection. Right from the first year, law students are required to master specific genres - legal dissertation, commentary on judgments, case studies - which demand writing skills that include understanding expectations and instructions, mobilizing legal knowledge and building well-structured arguments. However, many students experience persistent difficulties in these exercises. These difficulties are not simply due to inadequate language skills, but also to pre-existing representations of university writing, built up during high school or early academic experience. These representations have a profound influence on the way students approach the writing task, their understanding of teachers' expectations, and their ability to appropriate disciplinary standards. In a Moroccan context where methodological support is sometimes insufficient or limited, these representations can become a real obstacle to success.

Indeed, academic success in law studies depends to a large extent on students' ability to move beyond a simplified view of writing, often perceived as a mere exercise in repetition, in order to invest themselves fully in mastering academic genres and adopting an analytical and critical stance. The discrepancy between institutional expectations and student representations thus creates obstacles to learning that require special attention, both at the pedagogical level and in the design of support systems.

The aim of this work is to explore these student representations of academic writing in law, based on a study of a sample of Moroccan students, in order to gain a better understanding of the obstacles to the appropriation of legal genres. It also proposes a reflection on pedagogical avenues likely to facilitate the integration of academic standards, taking into account the specificities of the Moroccan context and discipline. Through this approach, the aim is to contribute to a better articulation between academic expectations and the real needs of students, with a view to improving and promoting their success. This study will address the following question:

- What representations do first-year law students have of academic writing, and in what way can these representations constitute an obstacle to learning the legal genres expected in their training?

2. Literature Review

2.1. Social representations of academic writing

The notion of social representation refers to a system of shared meanings that guides the way an individual perceives a situation or practice. As Guimelli (2009) points out, “social representations constitute a particular modality of knowledge, generally referred to as ‘common sense knowledge’, whose specificity lies in the social nature of the processes that produce them. They cover all the beliefs, knowledge and opinions shared by individuals in the same group with regard to a given social object” (p. 63). Applied to academic writing, this notion enables us to analyze how students construct their conception of what it means to “write well” at university.

Social representations of writing mobilize shared beliefs that influence students' writing choices and strategies. Bucheton and Soulé (2009) emphasize that these representations are part of a complex context combining knowledge, emotions and professional postures, thus having a strong impact on classroom learning and the appropriation of academic standards.

Although rarely formulated explicitly, these representations strongly condition the strategies mobilized during the writing process. Often handed down from high school onwards, they are rarely called into question when students enter higher education. Some students, for example, still see academic writing as simply a faithful rendition of the course or a personal statement of position. On the contrary, it's about mobilizing disciplinary knowledge in precise linguistic and argumentative forms.

Following on from this perspective, Philippe, Romainville and Willocq (1997) show that initial conceptions of learning guide the strategies adopted by students, and condition their adaptation to the new demands of university. This inadequate interpretation of expectations is a major obstacle to the appropriation of the academic genres expected in higher education.

This idea fits well with what Lea and Street (1998) call the « academic literacies » approach. They explain that when students enter university, they have to get used to new ways of reading, writing, and thinking that are specific to each subject. It's not just about picking up a set of technical skills, it's also about learning the ways of reasoning and communicating that matter in that field. In law, for example, this means more than knowing legal vocabulary; it's about understanding the unwritten rules and patterns of argument that shape legal writing

2.2. Gaps between instructions and student interpretations

Didactic research has shown that teaching instructions alone are not enough to ensure that students understand the task. There is often a gap between what the teacher asks for and what the student understands of the task. Bronckart (1996) points out that instructions are often perceived by students as mere tasks to be accomplished, leading to misunderstandings about real expectations and hindering the appropriation of specific discourse genres.

Bernard and Normand (1998) point out that students expect clearly defined assessment instructions, particularly concerning the type of questions and criteria on which they will be judged. They want to know in advance which dimensions will be assessed, such as comprehension, analysis or memorization. What's more, precise instructions encourage them to engage more authentically in qualitative assessments.

In law teaching, this type of discrepancy is common: students believe they are expected to reproduce the course, whereas the teacher is assessing their ability to develop an argument, select relevant notions and master the structure of the genre (commentary, dissertation, case study). This lack of alignment between instructions, perceived task and actual target task is an obstacle to learning.

2.3. Disciplinary genres in law: Specific language forms

Each academic discipline relies on textual genres that reflect its modes of thought, objectives and epistemic requirements. Delcambre and Lahanier-Reuter (2010) show that genres of academic writing are closely linked to disciplines, which complicates the task for students. These specificities, combined with changing requirements at different levels of study, create continuities and ruptures in their writing practices.

In law, these genres - such as the legal dissertation, commentary on judgments or case studies - call for a particular form of writing, requiring rigor, lexical precision, argumentative logic and analytical posture. However, these genres are rarely taught as learning objects. They are often approached by means of implicit instructions or after-the-fact corrections, with the idea that students will gradually learn to appropriate the codes by immersion. Even though they have neither a reference model nor the tools to decipher expectations.

2.4. Student perceptions of academic writing from L1 to L3 law: An obstacle to appropriation and the case for explicit pedagogical approaches

Throughout their university career, law students have to familiarize themselves with new and demanding codes, particularly in terms of writing practices. This applies to genres such as commentary on judgments, legal dissertations and case studies: textual forms that are often unfamiliar, highly standardized and generally taught implicitly. All the essays produced over the course of the bachelor's degree reveal frequent difficulties: uncertainty about the expected structure, hesitations about the language register, insufficiently developed authorial posture, and so on.

These difficulties are not solely linguistic or methodological in nature. They are frequently rooted in students' initial and persistent conceptions of academic writing. These conceptions, built up during high school or forged through successive academic experiences, are likely to result in incomplete or erroneous interpretations of instructions, inappropriate mobilization of knowledge, or even resistance to the expected forms of writing (Reuter, 2007). It therefore seems necessary to highlight these representations, not in order to sanction them, but to better understand their impact on the appropriation of disciplinary learning during the course of training. Blaser and Pollet (2010) explain that the appropriation of academic writing goes beyond the simple mastery of formal rules to include a thorough understanding of disciplinary expectations and an acculturation to implicit norms, requiring specific pedagogical support to enable students to build a genuine authorial posture. Along these lines, Garnier et al (2015) emphasize that training in academic writing must be based on a detailed understanding of students' language practices and the identification of the specific difficulties they encounter, in order to better support their appropriation of academic standards.

With this in mind, this research adopts an exploratory and longitudinal approach. It is based on a questionnaire designed for first-, second- and third-year law students in Morocco. The questionnaire aims to gather their conceptions of academic writing, their perceptions of legal genres and their needs for pedagogical support (Dolz & Schneuwly, 1998; Chartrand & Lord, 2013). The aim is twofold: firstly, to describe the dominant representations linked to disciplinary writing in law; secondly, to identify pedagogical courses of action to support their appropriation of these genres throughout the university curriculum.

This approach is in line with a desire to better articulate university pedagogy and the concrete experiences of students, by mobilizing contributions from the didactics of writing and the educational sciences (Reuter, 2007; Delcambre & Lahanier-Reuter, 2010; Bouchard & Perron, 2012).

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Research approach

This study is part of a descriptive, exploratory approach based on the educational sciences and university didactics. It aims to understand how law students enrolled in Moroccan universities perceive university writing, with no pretensions to statistical generalization. The aim is to identify trends, recurring conceptions, and even persistent misunderstandings, in order to fuel pedagogical reflection.

The approach adopted is both comprehensive and interpretative. Indeed, the aim is to welcome students' words as an entry point towards a better understanding of the invisible obstacles to learning academic writing, in a Moroccan higher education context where the demands of disciplinary rigor are often implicit.

3.2. Target audience

The questionnaire was distributed to a sample of 80 students enrolled in law degree courses at several Moroccan faculties. No level restrictions were imposed in order to cover all three years of the undergraduate degree "Licence" (L1, L2, L3) and to enable a cross-sectional reading of representations linked to academic writing in law.

3.3. Instruments and data collection

A structured questionnaire with multiple-choice questions was used for data collection. The questionnaire was distributed online to reach a large sample of students from several Moroccan faculties. Data collection was carried out over a three-month period, enabling a representative set of responses to be obtained.

We chose to use a structured quantitative questionnaire instead of qualitative methods like interviews because we wanted to spot general trends and common ideas among a large and varied group of law students, rather than focus on individual stories in depth. This approach made it possible to gather similar kinds of answers from students at different universities and study levels. However, this choice also has its limits. While the questionnaire gives a good

picture of overall patterns and shared challenges, it doesn't reveal the more detailed, personal reasons behind students' views and strategies. These aspects could be better explored in the future using qualitative methods, such as semi-structured interviews or focus groups.

4. Results

4.1. Respondent profile and writing experience

The sample for this study comprises 80 students enrolled in the Bachelor of Law program, divided relatively evenly between the three years of the university curriculum. The first year (L1) has 30 students (37.5%), the second year (L2) 28 students (35%), and the third year (L3) 22 students (27.5%). This balanced distribution offers a diversified view of representations and experiences according to students' level of seniority in legal training. Figure 1 presents the distribution of students by their current year of study.

Figure 1. Distribution of students by current year of study

As far as experience of academic writing is concerned, a large majority (77.5%) say they have already written a law paper, while 15% say they have never had this opportunity, and 7.5% are unsure. This result indicates that, despite the majority's experience, a not insignificant proportion of students remain unfamiliar with disciplinary written exercises, which may explain certain difficulties later on. Table 1 summarizes students' experience of writing university assignments in law.

Table 1. Experience of writing a university assignment in law

Question	Response	Number of Respondents	% of Respondents
Have you ever written a university-level written assignment in law?	Yes	62	77.5%
	No	12	15.0%
	I don't know	6	7.5%
	Total	80	100%

Finally, self-assessment of the methodological training received reveals a significant deficit: almost a third of students (27.5%) feel “not at all trained”, and 32.5% consider themselves “poorly trained”. Conversely, only 12.5% and 5% of students respectively consider their training to be “good” or “very good”. These data highlight a marked need for support and in-depth methodological training. Table 2 details students' self-assessed level of training in legal methodology.

Table 2. Level of training in legal methodology

Question	Level of Assessment	Number of Respondents	% of Respondents
To what extent do you feel you have been trained in the methodology of written legal exercises?	Not trained at all	22	27.5%
	Slightly trained	26	32.5%
	Moderately trained	18	22.5%
	Well trained	10	12.5%
	Very well trained	4	5.0%
	Total	80	100%

4.2. General representations of university writing

To understand students' initial conceptions of university writing, the question “Writing at university means first of all repeating the course” was asked. The results, presented in Figure 2, show that 55% of students (30% “strongly disagree” and 25% “somewhat disagree”) reject this idea. However, 25% of respondents (15% “tend to agree” and 10% “strongly agree”) subscribe to this reductionist vision, centered on the simple reproduction of course content.

Figure 2. Position on the statement “Writing is repeating the course”

This duality reflects an ambivalent representation of academic writing among students, a notable proportion of whom remain attached to a scholastic and unreflective approach to academic writing.

Furthermore, an evaluation of the dimensions deemed essential in academic writing reveals a diversity of conceptions. Students value mastery of the course as much as the construction of a rigorous legal argument, the avoidance of linguistic errors, the taking of a personal stance, and the ability to meet the implicit expectations of teachers. These results illustrate the complexity of representations of writing and the tensions between different perceived expectations.

4.3. Perception of clarity of instructions

Students were asked to rate their understanding of the expectations associated with three major legal genres: legal dissertation, case commentary and practical case. The results, shown in Figure 3, indicate that the majority scored between “moderately” and “very clearly” for each of the exercises, indicating a generally satisfactory understanding. Nevertheless, a sizeable proportion, ranging from 10 to 18% depending on the exercise, reported insufficient understanding, particularly for the commentary on a ruling, an exercise perceived as particularly complex.

Figure 3. Level of understanding of legal exercises

4.4. Conceptions of legal genres

An analysis of responses concerning the nature of legal exercises reveals significant and persistent confusion among students. As shown in Figure 4, in the case of case studies, just 31.2% of respondents were able to correctly identify that the main aim was to apply structured legal reasoning to solve a given problem. Conversely, a significant proportion of students attributed inaccurate purposes to the case study: 25% felt that it consisted essentially in expressing a personal opinion on the situation presented, while 31.2% reduced it to a simple exercise in summarizing a case. Finally, 12.5% of participants confessed to having no idea what this type of exercise entailed.

Figure 4. Students' representation of the case study

These results illustrate the extent of the conceptual misunderstandings surrounding academic legal genres. In the absence of explicit clarification of their characteristics, a majority of students remain trapped in imprecise or erroneous conceptions. These biased representations risk not only inducing misinterpretation of instructions, but also limiting their ability to construct arguments in line with disciplinary expectations. As a result, these confusions constitute a major obstacle to the gradual appropriation of writing genres in law, compromising their progress in learning and their academic success.

4.5. Difficulties encountered in legal exercises

Students report varying levels of difficulty in different types of legal exercise. As shown in Figure 5, the legal dissertation appears to be the most demanding exercise: over 60% of respondents say they find it “rather” or “very” difficult. Commentary on judgments also evokes a feeling of high complexity, with comparable proportions of students declaring moderate to high difficulty. In comparison, the practical case is perceived as slightly less problematic, although it remains a complex exercise: over 50% of students still mention a difficulty ranging from medium to high.

Figure 5. Level of difficulty encountered in legal exercises

These results, illustrated in the graph above, confirm that the normative and methodological requirements associated with these legal genres are a major obstacle for many students. They underline the need for explicit pedagogical support to help learners better understand what is expected and develop the writing skills specific to each type of writing.

4.6. Writing strategies adopted

The results relating to the writing strategies adopted by students in Table 3, show a diversity of behaviors. Among respondents, 47.5% say they “sometimes” to “always” repeat the course outline as is, while 47.5% say they ‘never’ or “rarely” do so. Similarly, preparing an outline before writing is adopted by 50% of students with a frequency of “sometimes” to “always”, while 50% use it little or not at all.

Table 3. Writing strategies adopted by students

Strategy	1. Never	2. Rarely	3. Sometimes	4. Often	5. Always	Total (N)
I follow the course plan as is	20 (25.0%)	18 (22.5%)	16 (20.0%)	14 (17.5%)	12 (15.0%)	80
I prepare an outline before writing	22 (27.5%)	18 (22.5%)	16 (20.0%)	12 (15.0%)	12 (15.0%)	80
I write all at once without organizing	10 (12.5%)	14 (17.5%)	20 (25.0%)	18 (22.5%)	18 (22.5%)	80
I try to organize my ideas before writing	18 (22.5%)	20 (25.0%)	16 (20.0%)	12 (15.0%)	14 (17.5%)	80

On the other hand, writing without prior organization seems to be a relatively frequent practice: 70% of students claim to do so at least “sometimes”, with 45% ‘often’ or “always”. Finally, 52.5% of students try to structure their ideas before writing, with a frequency ranging from “sometimes” to “always”.

These results suggest that, while some students adopt formalized strategies such as preparing an outline and structuring their ideas, a significant proportion nonetheless write without prior organization, which could be detrimental to the quality of their written output.

4.7. Educational support needs and expectations

Finally, students express a strong need for teaching support, as shown by their evaluations of the resources on offer in table 4. The small-group writing workshops were seen as fairly to very useful by 56.25% of respondents, while 50% considered the clear, illustrated methodological sheets to be fairly or very useful. Similarly, the annotated sample papers were positively rated by 66.25% of students, and the detailed feedback on submitted papers was deemed useful by 75%.

Table 4. Students' perceptions of the effectiveness of teaching aids

Educational Resource	1. Useless	2. Slightly useful	3. Quite useful	4. Very useful	Total (N)
Writing workshops in small groups	15 (18.75%)	20 (25.0%)	30 (37.5%)	15 (18.75%)	80
Clear and illustrated method sheets	10 (12.5%)	18 (22.5%)	28 (35.0%)	24 (30.0%)	80
Annotated model copies	12 (15.0%)	15 (18.75%)	25 (31.25%)	28 (35.0%)	80
Detailed feedback on submitted papers	8 (10.0%)	12 (15.0%)	30 (37.5%)	30 (37.5%)	80

These results illustrate a strong demand for explicit, interactive and personalized teaching methods, capable of supporting the gradual acquisition of the writing skills essential for academic success.

5. Discussion

The findings of this study show that many law students hold persistent and sometimes limiting views about academic writing. These ideas, often shaped by their high school experience, make it harder for them to engage with the specific legal genres required in their studies. A significant number still see academic writing mainly as repeating or summarizing the course content, which suggests they may not fully understand what legal writing actually demands. This narrow view can lead to a passive approach, reducing the level of critical thinking and structured argumentation needed at university.

The results also point to confusion about the main legal exercises – the dissertation, the case commentary, and the practical case. Many students are unsure what their teachers really expect, creating a gap between the task as intended and the task as completed. This is especially true for the case commentary, which requires careful, structured analysis but remains misunderstood by many. The practical case is also often misinterpreted, with some students seeing it as a personal opinion piece or a case summary instead of an exercise in applying legal reasoning to solve a problem.

One particularly interesting finding is the contradiction in students' writing strategies. Many say they try to organize their ideas before writing, yet a large number also admit to writing "all at once" without a plan. This suggests that while they know organization matters, they may lack clear methods to achieve it. As a result, they start with good intentions but end up writing in a single block – sometimes because they're unsure how to proceed, other times out of frustration.

This gap between intention and practice highlights the need for explicit instruction in planning techniques, such as making outlines, using visual organizers, or drafting in stages.

The results also confirm that many students feel underprepared when it comes to the specific demands of legal writing, and that current teaching methods do not always give them the practical tools they need. To address this, teaching could combine genre modeling and guided practice. For instance, genre modeling might involve showing students two case commentaries – one weak and one strong – and walking them through what makes the stronger one work, such as clear structure, precise terminology, and logical argumentation. Guided practice would then give them the chance to apply these features step by step, with feedback at each stage.

It could also be valuable to use innovative formats like microlearning, where students receive short, targeted lessons on specific skills. In legal writing, these could focus on things like building arguments, citing sources correctly, or writing introductions and conclusions. Short, focused activities can make learning more engaging and manageable, while helping students gradually build confidence and competence in the written skills their field requires.

Overall, these results point to the importance of teaching approaches that actively build skills and reshape students' initial views of writing, so they can move more smoothly from high school to university-level expectations.

Conclusion

This study sheds light on the persistent and sometimes misleading views that Moroccan law students hold about academic writing, as well as the practical and methodological challenges they face in mastering the legal genres central to their training. These conceptions, often inherited from high school, can lead to misunderstandings about tasks, a tendency to see writing as mere repetition, and difficulties in producing structured and analytical work.

The results reveal notable areas of confusion, particularly regarding the case commentary and practical case, and highlight a striking contradiction in writing strategies: many students say they try to organize their ideas, yet also report writing without a plan. This gap between intention and practice suggests that students often lack the concrete tools needed to turn awareness into effective action.

Addressing these issues calls for teaching approaches that are both explicit and practical. Strategies such as genre modeling—for example, comparing weak and strong case

commentaries to identify the features of effective writing—and guided practice with step-by-step feedback can help students internalize academic conventions and improve their work over time. Additionally, incorporating microlearning—short, targeted lessons on skills such as structuring arguments, using legal terminology accurately, or drafting introductions—can make learning more focused, engaging, and manageable.

By combining these methods, educators can not only improve students' technical skills but also help them rethink their understanding of academic writing, bridging the gap between secondary and university expectations. Such a shift is essential for enabling law students to fully participate in the intellectual and professional community of their discipline.

Disclosure Statement

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Notes on Contributors

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Appendix 1. Questionnaire on Law Students' Representations of Academic Writing

This questionnaire is part of a university research project on the representations, practices, and difficulties of law students in relation to academic writing. The answers collected, entirely anonymous and confidential, will be used solely for scientific analysis. No personal data will be recorded. The estimated completion time is about 5 minutes. Your participation is valuable and will help to better understand the need for methodological support. Thank you for your collaboration.

I- General Information

1. Current year of study

- L1 L2 L3

2. Have you ever written a university-level written assignment in law?

- Yes No I don't know

3. To what extent do you feel you have been trained in the methodology of written legal exercises (dissertation, case commentary, practical case)?

- 1 2 3 4 5

II- General Representations of Academic Writing

4. To what extent do you agree with the following statement: "Writing at university means first of all repeating the course"

- Strongly disagree 1 2 3

5. Writing a university paper is above all about:

- Showing that I have mastered the course 1 2 3
- Constructing a rigorous legal argument 1 2 3
- Avoiding language mistakes 1 2 3
- Giving my personal opinion 1 2 3
- Meeting the professor's implicit expectations 1 2 3

6. How comfortable are you with writing a university paper in law?

- Not at all comfortable 1 2 3 4 5 Very comfortable

7. To what extent do written assignments stress you out?

Not at all 1 2 3 4 5 Extremely

III- Representations of Legal Genres

8. To what extent do you understand what is expected in each of the following exercises?

(1 = Not at all / 5 = Very clearly)

- Legal dissertation 1 2 3 4 5

- Case commentary 1 2 3 4 5

- Practical case 1 2 3 4 5

9. A case commentary mainly consists of:

- Rewriting the decision in your own words
- Summarizing the facts and the ruling
- Analyzing it in a structured way according to legal criteria
- I don't know

10. A legal dissertation mainly consists of:

- Writing freely on a topic
- Summarizing the course related to the topic
- Constructing a solid and structured legal argument
- I don't know

11. A practical case mainly consists of:

- Giving your personal opinion on a situation
- Summarizing a case
- Applying legal reasoning to solve a problem
- I don't know

IV- Perceived Difficulties and Support**12.** To what extent do you have difficulties with these exercises?

(1 = No difficulty / 5 = A lot of difficulty)

- Legal dissertation 1 2 3 4 5- Case commentary 1 2 3 4 5- Practical case 1 2 3 4 5**13.** To what extent do you agree with the following statements:

(1 = Strongly disagree / 5 = Strongly agree)

- I don't know what teachers really expect 1 2 3 4 5- I lack a method to structure my writing 1 2 3 4 5- Legal language is difficult to understand and use 1 2 3 4 5- I would like to have more models or concrete examples 1 2 3 4 5**14.** Your current strategies when you have to write

(1 = Never / 5 = Always)

- I follow the course outline exactly 1 2 3 4 5- I prepare an outline before writing 1 2 3 4 5- I write everything at once without organizing 1 2 3 4 5- I try to organize my ideas before writing 1 2 3 4 5**15.** Perceived usefulness of certain teaching aids

(1 = Useless / 4 = Very useful)

- Small-group writing workshops 1 2 3 4- Clear and illustrated method sheets 1 2 3 4- Annotated model papers 1 2 3 4- Detailed feedback on submitted papers 1 2 3 4